

PREPARATION OF SOMARAJI TAILA

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ABSTRACT

In *Bhaishajya Kalpana*, both *Aushadha Kalpana* and *Ahara Kalpana* are included. The fundamental preparations under *Aushadha Kalpana* are collectively termed *Panchvidha Kashaya Kalpana*. Since these formulations generally have a short shelf life, different methods are adopted to enhance their stability, therapeutic efficacy, and storage period. Such modified dosage forms are known as secondary *Kalpana*, which include *Churna*, *Vati*, *Taila*, *Ghrita*, *Sandhan*, and *Avaleha Kalpana*. Among them, *Sneha Kalpana* is one of the most widely used dosage forms in day-to-day *Ayurvedic* practice. The four types of *Sneha Dravyas* are *Ghrita*, *Taila*, *Vasa*, and *Majja*. Here, *Sneha* refers to fat or fatty substances, while *Kalpana* denotes the pharmaceutical process that transforms these substances into medicines. *Somaraji Taila*, referenced in *Chakradatta*, *Bhaishajya Ratnavali*, AFI, and *Ayurveda Sara Sangraha*, is regarded as a drug of choice in

conditions such as *Kustha*, *Pama*, and *Nilika*. It is a polyherbal formulation prepared with ingredients like *Bakuchi*, *Haridra*, *Daruharidra*, *Sarsapa*, *Kustha*, *Karanja*, *Chakramarda*, *Aragvadha*, *Sarsapa Taila*, and cow's urine. The present paper provides a review of the ingredients of *Somaraji Taila* along with their probable mode of action.

KEYWORDS: *Sneha Kalpana, Taila Kalpana, Kustha, Pama.*

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, known as the “Science of Life,” is one of the oldest and most holistic systems aimed at promoting health and longevity, with origins tracing back to the very beginning of human life. In Indian tradition, good health is regarded as the foundation for achieving material, social, and spiritual progress. It is said that *Lord Brahma*, the creator of the universe, was also the first teacher of *Ayurveda*.^[1] *Ayurveda* has two main objectives – to preserve the health of the healthy (*Swasthasya Swasthya Rakshanam*) and to cure the diseases of the sick (*Aturasya Vikara Prashamaanam*). It not only helps in restoring the health of patients but also promotes overall well-being.^[2] Between the 8th and 9th centuries, *Ayurveda* underwent a significant transformation with the emergence and advancement of *Rasashastra*.^[3] *Rasashastra* is a highly significant branch of *Ayurveda* that focuses on the use of metals, minerals, and herbo-mineral formulations in medicinal preparations.^[4] *Bhaishajya* means medicine and *Kalpana* refers to its formulation; therefore, *Bhaishajya Kalpana* is the branch of *Ayurveda* concerned with the preparation of medicines using herbal drugs, such as *Churna, Gutika, Vati, Taila, Ghrita, Lepa, Aasva, and Arista*.^[5] *Sneha Kalpana* represents one of the fundamental and frequently prescribed dosage forms in *Ayurveda*. The term is derived from the combination of *Sneha* and *Kalpana*. The *Sneha Dravyas* employed in this context are broadly classified into four categories, namely *Ghrita, Taila, Vasa, and Majja*.^[6]

Taila Kalpana, a type of *Sneha Kalpana*, includes the formulation *Somaraji Taila*, which is prepared using extracts of traditional herbs such as *Bakuchi, Haridra, Daruharidra, Sarsapa, Kustha, Karnja Bija, Chakramarda Bija, Aragvadha Patra*, along with *Sarsapa Taila* and cow’s urine. This oil is primarily indicated in *Kustha Roga* and is applied externally. Due to its rapid absorption through the skin, even in small quantities, *Somaraji Taila* offers effective and safe protection against bacterial infections.

DRUG REVIEW

Table 1: Rasa Panchaka of ingredients.

S. No.	Ingredients	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Vipaka	Karma
1	<i>Bakuchi</i>	<i>Katu, Tikta</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksa</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kusthaghna, Vranshodhan, Vranropana</i>
2	<i>Haridra</i>	<i>Tikta, Katu</i>	<i>Ruksa,</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Krimghana, Kusthagana, Varnya</i>
3	<i>Daruharidra</i>	<i>Madhura,</i>	<i>Laghu,</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kapha- Pittahara, Chedana</i>

		<i>Amla</i>	<i>Ruksha</i>			
4	<i>Sarsapa</i>	<i>Katu, Tikta</i>	<i>Tikshna, Snigdha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kapha-vatahara, Dipana, Hridya</i>
5	<i>Kustha</i>	<i>Katu, Tikta</i>	<i>Laghu</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kaphavatajit, Shukarla, Varnya, Raktashodhaka, Varnya</i>
6	<i>Karanja</i>	<i>Katu, Tikta</i>	<i>Tikshna</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kusthaghna, Krimijit, Varnashodhana</i>
7	<i>Chakramarda</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Lekhan, Kusthaghna, Krimighna</i>
8	<i>Aragvadha</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Mrdu, Guru, Snigdha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Kusthaghna, Vednasthapan, Dahaparshman</i>
9	<i>Aragvadha Patra</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Mrdu</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Kapha- Meda vishopshan</i>
10.	<i>Sarsapa Taila</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Laghu</i>	<i>Usna, Tikshna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kustha, Krimi, Koth, Dustha krimi</i>
11.	<i>Cow' Urine</i>	<i>Katu, Tikta, Kasaya</i>	<i>Laghu</i>	<i>Usna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kustha, Kasa, Kamala, Pandu</i>

METERIAL AND MATHAD

1. **SARSAPA TAILA MURCHANA**- *Sarsapa Taila Murchana* will be carried out according to *Bhaishajya Ratnavali*.^[7]

Table 2: Ingredients of Sarsapa Taila Murchana.

S. N	Ingredients	Quantity given as per reference of <i>Bhaishajya Ratnavali</i>	Quantity taken
1.	<i>Amalaki</i>	1 Karsh (12gm)	48 gm
2.	<i>Haridra</i>	1 Karsh (12gm)	48 gm
3.	<i>Nagarmotha</i>	1 Karsh (12gm)	48 gm
4.	<i>Bilvamula Twak</i>	1 Karsh (12gm)	48 gm
5.	<i>Dadim</i>	1 Karsh (12gm)	48 gm
6.	<i>Nagkeshar</i>	1 Karsh (12gm)	48 gm
7.	<i>Krishna Jeerak</i>	1 Karsh (12gm)	48 gm
8.	<i>Sugandhbala</i>	1 Karsh (12gm)	48 gm
9.	<i>Naluka</i>	1 Karsh (12gm)	48 gm
s10.	<i>Vibhitaki</i>	1 Karsh (12gm)	48 gm
11.	<i>Manjistha</i>	2 Pala (96gm)	384 gm
12.	<i>Sarsapa Taila</i>	1 Prastha (750 ml)	4 Prastha (3liter)
13.	Water	1 Aadhaka (4) Part	12 Liter

- *Sarsapa Taila* should be heated on low flame and cooked till it starts foaming. Then the vessel should be taken off the flame, the above mentioned *Aushadhi* from *Amalaki* to *Vibhitaki* should be coarsely ground in the mortar and pestle.
- Then take them in a vessel, add some water and make a *Kalka*, Then *Manjistha* should be coarsely ground and its *Kalka* should also be made.
- Then this *Kalka* should be poured into *Sarsapa Taila*.

- Then the above-mentioned amount of water adds.
- Then the *Sarsapa Taila* should be cooked till it show the sign of *Sneha Sidhi*.
- When shows the *Sneha Sidhi Lakshna* the vessel should be taken off flame and *Sarsapa Taila* must be filtered.
- This will be used for preparing of *Somaraji Taila*.

2. SOMARAJI TAILA PREPARATION

Somaraji Taila will be prepared according to *Chakradatta*.^[8]

Table No. 3: Composition of Ingredients of *Somaraji Taila*.

S.N.	Raw Drugs	Part used	Forms	Quantity
1.	<i>Bakuchi</i>	Seed	<i>Kalka Dravya</i>	1 Part (28gm)
2.	<i>Haridra</i>	Rhizome	<i>Kalka Dravya</i>	1 Part (28gm)
3.	<i>Daruharidra</i>	Stem	<i>Kalka Dravya</i>	1 Part (28gm)
4.	<i>Sarsapa</i>	Seed	<i>Kalka Dravya</i>	1 Part (28gm)
5.	<i>Aragvadha</i>	Pericarp	<i>Kalka Dravya</i>	1 Part (28gm)
6.	<i>Kustha</i>	Root	<i>Kalka Dravya</i>	1 Part (28gm)
7.	<i>Karanja</i>	Seed	<i>Kalka Dravya</i>	1 Part (28gm)
8.	<i>Chakramarda</i>	Seed	<i>Kalka Dravya</i>	1 Part (28gm)
9.	<i>Aragvadha</i>	Leaf	<i>Kalka Dravya</i>	1 Part (28gm)
10.	<i>Sarsapa Taila</i>	Seed	<i>Sneha</i>	4 Part (1.5liter)
11.	Cow's Urine	Urine	Liquid	1 <i>Prastha</i>
12.	Water	Liquid	Liquid	6 liters

- All Above the *Kalka Dravyas* (*Bakuchi* to *Aragvadha*) should be coarsely powder and converted into *Kalka* form.
- Then adding little amount of water in *Kalka Dravyas*. After this, heat the Murchit *Sarsapa Taila* by putting it in a stain less steel vessel.
- When the foam subsides take the vessel off the Agni and the put the mentioned ingredients in the *Sarsapa Taila*.
- After this *Paka* must be done till attains *Taila Sidhi Lakshna*. Prepared *Somaraji Taila* must be filtered and store the container after cooling.

Method of Use- External Application.

PARIKSHA^[9]

- *Varti*- When the *Kalka* is rubbed with the middle finger, index finger and thumb. It forms *Varti* like pattern.
- *Phenodgama*- The *Taila* begins to foam.

- *Shabda Pariksha* – When the *Kalka* is dropped on flame.
- He gets burn without any *Shabda* (without creaking sound)
- *Samyak Gandh Varna Rasaadinam* – In *Sneha* proper production of smell, colour, taste.

RESULT AND OBSERVATIONS

The result and observations are mentioned in Table no. 4,5 shows loss of taila after Sarsapa Taila Murchhana as well as Somaraji Taila preparation.

Table No. 4: Result and observations of Sarsapa Taila Murchhana.

S.N	Quantity Taken	Quantity obtained	Time taken	Loss in ml	Loss in %
1.	3 liters	2.2 liters	3 days	800 ml	26.66

Table No. 5: Result and observations of Somaraji Taila.

S.N	Quantity Taken	Quantity obtained	Time taken	Loss in ml	Loss in %
1.	1.5 liters	1.2 liters	3 days	300ml	20

Some other observations are following

- During preparation it should become sludge like structure and attain the characteristic colour of *Somaraji Taila*.
- The *Kalka* should look like dense, smooth and roundish mass. When rolled between two fingers it should separate from the layers of *Taila*. The *Kalka* should become like a wick.
- When the *Kalka* is sprinkled on the flame, there should be no cracking sound.
- The Characteristic colour and odour should be appear.

DISCUSSION

The advancement of medical science has led to the development of numerous drugs for disease management across various fields. However, despite significant progress, certain areas still lack effective medicines with minimal side effects. Skin disorders remain one such challenging domain. Ayurveda, on the other hand, emphasizes holistic healing of the body with the aim of providing overall benefits. In *Ayurvedic* texts, skin diseases are classified under *Kustha*, which is further divided into *Maha Kustha* and *Kshudra Kustha*.

Through the process of *Sanskar*, the qualities of medicines are modified and enhanced, thereby improving their therapeutic potential. This makes *Sneha Kalpana* (oil/ghee formulations) highly significant. Depending on the disease, *Sneha Kalpana* can be administered internally as *Paan*, *Nasya*, and *Anuvasana Basti*, or externally as *Abhyanga*. Among these preparations, *Somaraji Taila* is a notable formulation prescribed for treating 18

types of *Kustha*, including *Maha Kustha* and *Kshudra Kustha*. Conditions such as *Nilika*, *Viplava*, *Vyangya*, *Gambhira Vatarakta*, *Kandu*, *Nyach*, *Kachu*, *Pama*, and *Nadidhustvarna* are mentioned by *Acharya Chakradatta* as effectively managed by this herbal oil.

CONCLUSION

Somaraji Taila is well documented in *Ayurvedic* literature as a highly effective remedy for *Kustha* with proven efficacy in treating both *Maha Kustha* and *Kshudra Kustha* in a short span of time. Each ingredient in this formulation possesses significant action against skin disorders. The oil is recommended only for external application, particularly in the form of *abhyanga* and is not intended for internal use. Promoting further research into the pharmacological effects of its ingredients for disease prevention, this review also helps in understanding the diverse therapeutic actions of each component of *Somaraji Taila*.

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